

SOME NICKNAMES ARE MENTIONED IN THE WORKS OF “RELICS FROM ANCIENT NATIONS”

Mirzakhmedova Oygul Abdirashidovna

Doctoral student of Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13932917>

Abstract: The article discusses the lexical-semantic analysis of some nicknames used in the work of the great scientist Abu Rayhan Beruni "Relics from Ancient Nations".

Key words: nicknames, onomastic unit, Zulqarnayn, Kayumars, historical text, famous names, manuscript.

One form of ambiguity is nicknames given to other people. Nicknames, like nicknames, refer to a person with a second name. Nicknames often occur together with a person's first name and in this respect are similar to a surname and a patronymic.

Nicknames express the desires, profession and nationality of each person, and nicknames express the work activity, shortcomings and some features of the body of each person. There are different ways to give a nickname: it depends on the different characteristics of a person. Accordingly, nicknames indicate a person's clan or tribe affiliation, his physical defects, character, profession, nationality, the first job he held in that village, and similar good and bad qualities and characteristics.

In the work “Relics from Ancient Nations”, the scientist focused on the nicknames Zulqarnayn, Kayumars, Zulaktof and their meaning.

Zulqarnain (Arabic: two-horned) is the name of the king who, according to ancient traditions widespread among Muslims, conquered the lands of Chin (China) of the world and erected a huge barrier on the path of Gog and Magog. He was believed to be the ruler of the East and the West, or that he was so called because the two edges of his crown were horn-shaped . Chapter IV of the work “Relics from Ancient Nations” is entitled “On the differences of different nations in determining the [identity] of the king who was nicknamed Zularnain.”

Zulqarnayn's efforts to establish justice on earth are described in the Quran. Some Islamic researchers (e.g. Ibn al-Asir) interpret the Dhul-Qarnain mentioned in the Holy Quran as Alexander of Macedonia, others as a completely different person who lived before Hazrat Ibrahim (as) .

The short explanatory dictionary of historical terms gives the following explanation: Alexander the Great is the nickname of Alexander the Great, and Alexander the Great was called Alexander the Great in Central Asia . Alexander lived between 356 and 323 BC. BC

In the work "Relics of the Ancient Nations" there are also opinions that Alexander received this nickname because he wore a two-crown crown: [Some] say that there was a man named Zulqarnayn Artrakis. He fought against Samirus, one of the kings of Babylon. Eventually he won, killed him and scalped him along with his hair and two cockatiels. That's why he was given the nickname Zulqarnayn .

Beruni, citing various information about Zulqarnayn's nicknames, expressed the opinion that there are often people with Zul nicknames in Yemen and writes that Zulqarnayn may have originated from Yemen: Among these words, the last one seems to be correct. Because "zu" [people with nicknames] only come from Yemen and cannot be found in other places. Their names could not do without the word "to". For example, Zulmanor, Zulaz'or, Zu-sh-Shanotir, Zu-Nuvos, Zu-Jadan, Zu-Yazan and others . In the explanation of the work it is said that to means "owner", "possessor" .

Kayumars is the name of the first king of Iran. Beruni writes that Kayumars were nicknamed "Girshah" (Mountain King) and "Gilshah" (Loyshah). The Persians call Kayumars the first man. His nickname is "Girshah," which means "King of the Mountain." Some say "Gilshah," which means "King of the Mud." Because no one was there at that time. Kayumars means "live, speak," .

Zulaktof is the nickname of the Sassanid Emperor Shopur II: this incident is said to have occurred during the reign of Shopur Zul-Aktof .

Onomastic unit analysis is an important process for studying handwritten texts of the historical period. Famous names in historical texts, manuscripts and inscriptions serve as an important document for the study of ancient and modern history and at the same time are inexhaustible sources for onomastic research.

References:

1. Абу Райҳон Беруний. Қадимги халқлардан қолган ёдгорликлар (Осор ал-боқия). I жилд. –Тошкент: O'zbekiston, 2020.
2. Абу Райҳон Беруний. Қадимги халқлардан қолган ёдгорликлар (Осор ал-боқия). I жилд. –Тошкент: O'zbekiston, 2022
3. Исмоилов М., Шаропов А. Тарих атамалари луғати. – Тошкент: Академнашр, 2013. – Б. 174.
4. Назаров Қ. Жаҳон фалсафаси қомуси. Биринчи китоб. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон файласуфлари миллий жамияти, 2022. – Б. 419.
5. Ўзбекистон Миллий Энциклопедияси. 4-жилд. –Тошкент: ЎзМЭ, 2002. – Б. 45.

6. Чориев З. Тарих атамаларининг қисчқача изоҳли луғати. – Тошкент: Академия, 2002. – Б. 99.

